

CHARACTERISTICS OF FREE EDGE DELAMINATION IN ANGLE-PLY LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the fundamental nature of free-edge delamination is investigated for an angle-ply laminate subjected to uniform displacement and thermal loading. The strain energy release rate for the delaminated composites with various laminate parameters was calculated using a quasi-three dimensional finite element method and a modified crack closure integral. A simple failure criterion was formulated to evaluate the effect of delamination on the tensile strength of angle-ply laminate with small fiber orientations. Finally, experimental observations were made and compared with theoretical predictions.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important parameters to be considered in designing fibre reinforced composite structures is delamination occurred between layers, since many applications of such structures involve this problem. It is known to cause structural disintegration, stiffness reduction and especially failure at stresses well below the strength levels expected for defect free material. Rotem and Hashin[1] identified three distinct failure modes in angle-ply laminate. They pointed out that delamination is the major failure mechanism for fiber angles less than 45. In 1981, R. Y. Kim[2] investigated the strength of angle-ply laminate and compared the results with the tensor polynomial failure criterion[3]. Experimental data on the strength agree reasonably well with the failure theory except for the small fiber orientations under tension. Two reasons for the low strength results for small angles can be explained as follows. A "scissor action" type of twisting between the plies induce high transverse stresses and strains which contribute to failure at relatively low tensile load. Another cause of early failure may be the interlaminar stresses occurred in the edge region because considerable interlaminar separation and cracking were found in failed specimens.

Analytical studies[4,5] have shown that the state of stress in the vicinity of the free edge of such a laminate is fully three dimensional and may not be predicted by laminated plate theory. These results show that interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , may dominates free edge delamination in [$\pm\theta$]s laminate. Recent results reported by S. S. Wang[6] provided the

fundamental nature of free edge delamination in angle-ply laminate subjected to uniform axial extension. Fracture mechanics parameters such as stress intensity factors and associated strain energy release rate are defined and effect of delamination length, fiber orientation, lamination and geometric variables were considered. However, a systematic discussion of the relationship between the tensile strength of angle-ply laminate for small fiber orientations and free edge delamination has never been presented in our opinion.

In this paper, the stability of delamination crack is investigated for angle-ply laminate subjected to uniform axial strain and thermal loading. Since composite laminates undergo a uniform thermal loading associated with cooling the laminate from processing temperature, significant residual thermal interlaminar stresses to cause failure of layers within laminate can be developed[7]. And the effect of delamination crack on the tensile strength for small fiber orientations is evaluated by using a rule of mixtures and energy release rate concept in classical fracture mechanics. Due to the complexities of the problem, a quasi-three dimensional finite element method is used to obtain energy release rate associated with delamination growth. Finally, experimental observations were made and compared with theoretical results to assess the prediction accuracy of the delamination growth model.

ANALYTICAL METHOD

Finite element model

The angle-ply laminate in this study is modeled as an assembly of anisotropic plies separated by thin isotropic interface layers as shown in Fig. 1. The interface layer is assumed to have a uniform thickness of one-tenth of the individual ply thickness[10]. Two reasons for such a model are as follows . First, the delamination fracture surface analysis[6,7] shows that delamination crack propagates mainly along the resin-rich interlaminar region. Another reason is the oscillatory stress singularity observed at the interface where anti-plane shear stress is dominant[14]. The well known physical absurdity of crack face inter-penetration can be eliminated by introducing the homogeneous elastic interface layer which is more realistic than ideal interface condition[15]. In this model, the delamination crack is assumed to grow in the interface layer.

For a symmetric composite laminate under uniform axial strain or uniform change in temperature, the displacement field is as follows[4,5].

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= e_0 \cdot x + U(y,z) \\
 v &= V(y,z) \\
 w &= W(y,z)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where e_0 is a prescribed uniform axial strain. A quasi three dimensional finite element analysis similar to the Ref.[5] was used for this solution. Only one quarter of the cross section was modeled due to symmetry condition. Four noded quadrilateral, isoparametric elements with three degrees of freedom per node was used and interface layer was modeled with two elements through its thickness. The growth of delamination crack is simulated by replacing the crack tip node with two separated node to

incrementally extend the crack. As delamination crack length, a , was increased, the mesh refinement was changed accordingly to maintain the crack growth interval constant. The typical finite element model shown in Fig. 1 has 257 nodes and 216 elements, where the crack growth interval, Δ , a/h , is .2. This shows a good convergence in the solution of the energy release rate under the assumption of effective modulus[14].

Strain energy release rate

Strain energy release rates were calculated using a modified crack closure integral similar to that in reference[13]. The forces transmitted through the node at the crack tip and the relative displacements at the crack tip after the crack growth were used to calculate the energy required to close the crack. This technique greatly simplifies the computation of energy release rate because knowledge of the singular stress field is not required. Since it is noted that poor results were obtained when this method was used with higher order elements[13], four-noded element was used. In the assumption of linear elasticity, the mechanical and thermal loading effect can be superposed after the solutions are obtained respectively. Numerical results have shown that the total energy release rate, G_{Tot} is proportional to the thickness of laminate. So it can be expressed to the form independent of thickness.

$$G_{Tot}/h = (G_I + G_{II} + G_{III})/h = \bar{G}_m \cdot e_0^2 + \bar{G}_{mt} \cdot e_0 \cdot \Delta T + G_t \cdot (\Delta T)^2 \tag{2}$$

where G_m , G_{mt} and G_t are the strain energy release rates due to mechanical, thermal and superposition of these two loadings respectively.

Fig.1 Basic configuration and finite element model.

Tensile strength prediction.

The effect of constraint between plies with different fiber orientations is best illustrated by computing the ultimate tensile strength of $[\pm\theta]_s$ angle-ply laminate with the off-axis strength of unidirectional lamina. Fibers are seen to carry more load in angle-ply laminates than in uni-directional laminae. The constraint between adjacent plies manifest itself in the interlaminar stresses. If complete delamination occurs, the strength of angle-ply laminate should reduce to that of off axis lamina. Therefore, an equation for the strength of partially delaminated angle ply laminate can be developed using the rule of mixtures.

Free edge delaminations were assumed to exist at both edges along θ and $-\theta$ interfaces from the stress analysis. By assuming the laminated and delaminated regions of specimen act as independent components loaded in parallel and the failure strains of two portions are nearly equal because final fracture occurs just after delamination initiation[15,16]. Then the resultant load, P_r , carried by the specimen is the sum of the loads carried by the two portions.

$$P_r = P_a + P_o \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the reduced angle-ply strength, σ_r , due to delamination can be predicted from the angle-ply strength, σ_a , without delamination, the strength difference, $S(\theta)$, between angle-ply and off-axis laminate and the delamination length, a^*/b , just before final fracture.

$$\sigma_r = \sigma_a - S(\theta) \cdot a^*/b \quad (4)$$

where a and $S(\theta)$ can be obtained from laminated plate theory and first ply failure criterion. But the final crack length, a^* , is to be determined from the energy release rate analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The material system used in this study was graphite/epoxy prepreg tape. The thickness of the cured panel was approximately 1.1 mm corresponding to eight prepreg layer laminated according to $[\theta/-\theta]_s$, with $\theta = 10, 15, 20$ and 30 degree. The panels were cut by diamond saw to a specimen length of 20 cm and width of 1.25 to 2.0 cm. Five specimens were prepared for each fiber orientation and their free edges were polished to facilitate visual observation with an optical microscope. All specimens were painted with a white color so that initiation of failure could be easily detected by appearing black against a white color.

Tension tests were conducted on a 10 ton Instron Universal Test Machine at a controlled displacement rate of .25mm/min. Two specimens for each fiber orientation were unloaded just before final failure and the deply technique[17] was used to detect the extent of delamination. Finally, the delamination fracture surfaces were examined using scanning electron microscopy(SEM) to understand the mechanism of delamination.

RESULTS

Characteristics of energy release rate.

Material elastic constants of typical high modulus graphite/epoxy systems[4,5] were used in the present analysis. The effect of laminate width on the behavior of delamination crack growth was investigated. The results of S. S. Wang[6] indicate that stable crack growth region extends and the maximum value of G occurs at a delamination length approximately equal to one or two ply thickness as the width is increased. But from a careful examination of these results, we found that the non-dimensionalized location of maximum value and shape of G -curve with a/b is nearly independent of the laminate width. This trend was also confirmed from our computations for these laminate. Therefore, the case of $b/h=8$ was considered for the computational economy.

The strain energy release rate component, \bar{G}_m , with delamination lengths and fiber orientations is plotted in Fig. 2. This figure shows that the shape of energy release rate component, \bar{G}_m , is independent of fiber orientation in this laminate. The maximum value of G_m occurs approximately at the crack length of $a/b = .28$ and its magnitude with fiber orientation is maximum in $[\pm 15]_s$ laminate. We can expect that a delamination crack grows abruptly to a finite size of crack because \bar{G}_m increases rapidly with crack length near the free edge. Fig. 3 and 4 show that the behavior of \bar{G}_{mt} and \bar{G}_t can be identified two distinct modes according to the fiber orientations. G_{mt} and \bar{G}_t for the $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate are different in the locations of their maximum value, .60 and .65 respectively, compared with other laminates where the locations are about .70 and .75 respectively. The trend of maximum value of \bar{G}_m , \bar{G}_{mt} and \bar{G}_t can be explained from following facts. A mismatch in engineering properties between layers is the fundamental reason for the presence of interlaminar stresses, which result in delamination[18]. It was shown that the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficient, α_{xy} , has a maximum value in $[\pm 45]_s$ systems but the mismatch of mutual influence coefficient has a strong influence on delamination with fiber orientation in the 10-15 degree range. Consequently \bar{G}_m increases as fiber orientation approaches to approximately 15 and \bar{G}_t has a maximum value at 45 degree. \bar{G}_{mt} is supposed to have maximum value at the intermediate angle between these two extremes. And the minus value of \bar{G}_{mt} is due to the fact that the thermal residual stress, τ_{xz} , due to temperature drop has the opposite sign of that due to tensile loading. All these components show an unstable region, then a stable region where an increasing load is needed to increase delamination length.

Although, mode I, II and III components exist for an edge delamination in angle-ply laminate, mode III component is several order of magnitude higher than the other two components. These results agree with that the interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} , is very large compared to τ_{yz} and σ_z components.

Delamination initiation and growth

A macroscopic delamination crack will form at the interface layer between θ and $-\theta$ layer when the total strain energy release rate, G_{Tot} , for a small preexisting interface defects attain the critical value for the interface material. Since linear elastic fracture mechanics are based on an existing flaw length, a characteristic length of flaws should be

Fig.2 Variation of strain energy release rate due to mechanical loading with crack lengths and fiber orientations.

determined to be used in the prediction of delamination initiation. In this analysis, the characteristic length is assumed to be about one ply thickness[19]. The fracture criteria of delamination crack can be written as

$$G_{\text{Tot}} = G_{(I,II,III)c} \quad (5)$$

Experimental value for the mixed mode energy release rate is generally not available for composite laminates due to the difficulty in fracture test. Since, in angle-ply laminate, mode III component is primarily responsible for the delamination and the critical energy release rate of mode II can be used to conservatively estimate the criticality of mode III behavior[20], the fracture criteria can be written as

$$G_{\text{Tot}} = G_{\text{IIc}} \quad (6)$$

In this analysis the value of G_{IIc} is taken as 3.0 psi-in in the average concept from experimental values[21,22]. This value of G_c may result in low delamination onset strain but may have no effect on the stability characteristics, that is, determination of final crack length(a^*) before total fracture.

The delamination onset strains with delamination length for [± 15]s laminate are shown in Fig. 5. The effect of residual stress due to temperature drop and loading types can be observed. Similar behavior was also found for [± 30]s and [± 45]s. Since composites are cured at an elevated temperature, thermal stresses are always present. For a negative change in temperature, the thermal residual stresses, τ_{xz} , has the opposite sign of that due to tensile loading and hence the effect tend to prohibit the initiation and growth of delamination and vice versa under compressive loading. The effect of thermal residual stresses on the magnitude of delamination onset strain is less than 10 percent. But delamination onset strain is independent of loading type in the absence of thermal residual stresses. Under tensile loading with temperature drop, delamination onset

Fig.3 Variation of strain energy release rate due to combined effect of mechanical and thermal loading with crack lengths and fiber orientations.

Fig.4 Variation of strain energy release rate due to thermal loading with crack lengths and fiber orientations.

Fig.5 Delamination onset strain as a function of crack lengths in $[\pm 15/-15]_s$ laminate.

strain is nearly equal in the range of $a/b < .4$, and increases monotonically as delamination exceeds this range. Therefore, once any initial delamination is occurred, it may be arrested before total fracture

From the experimental observations the final fracture of laminate occurs just after delamination initiation, so a^*/b may have the value in the range of $a/b < .4$. However, under compressive loading, unstable crack growth region extends to the crack length about $a/b = .6$ and then shows stable behavior. Therefore, delamination can be easily initiated and grow more unstably and the presence of delamination is more detrimental to the strength of angle ply laminates than tensile loading. Fig. 6 shows the tensile strength of angle ply laminate for small fiber orientations. Failure criterion shows about 20 percent overestimated values for orientations less than 30 degree but the predicted values agree well with the experimental results for $a^*/b = .3$.

The relationship between the delamination and ply failure strain in this laminate shows that for small fiber orientations less than 30 , delamination precedes the laminate failure but the failure of delaminated region (θ -ply) is imminent. The effect of delamination on the redistribution of inplane stress components is presented in Fig. 7. The state of stress component perpendicular to the fiber direction, σ_{22} , changes from compression to tension and increases sharply close to the delamination crack tip. Also, in-plane shear stress, σ_{12} , increases near the crack tip. It shows that the increase of σ_{12} and especially σ_{22} may be a significant factor for transverse cracking due to delamination. Similar trends were found in all laminates considered in this study. These interaction between edge delamination and ply failure affect the tensile strength, final fracture, as observed in experiments.

Experimental results

The material properties used for this experiment are given in Table 1. Fig. 8 shows that plies with different fiber orientations separated by

Fig.6 Tensile strength of angle-ply laminate with fiber orientations.

Fig.7 In-Plane stress redistribution due to delamination.

Fig.8 Microstructure of Gr/epoxy composites.

resin-rich interlaminar region. The comparison of test results and predictions from theoretical model is given in Table 2. The elastic modulus was in good agreement with lamination theory[23]. The measured stress-strain responses of these laminates were essentially linear to failure except [± 30]s specimen. The slight non-linearity observed in [± 30]s specimen was associated with transverse cracking which was prior to delamination and progressive with loading. However, the ultimate strengths range from 20 to 40 percent lower than that of failure theory[3] in the fiber orientations less than 30. The largest decrease was found in the $\theta = 10$ specimen in which the strength difference, $S(\theta)$, between angle-ply and off-axis laminate is largest. The discrepancy between theory and

Table 1 Material Properties of Graphite/Epoxy Composites

$E_{11} = 117.7$ (Gpa)
$E_{22} = 6.8$ (Gpa)
$G_{12} = 4.2$ (Gpa)
$\nu_{12} = 0.27$
$X_T = X_c = 1320$ (Mpa)
$Y_T = 31$ (Mpa) $Y_c = 164$ (Mpa)
$S^T = 43$ (Mpa)

experiment is believed due to the free edge delamination initiated at stresses approximately 90 percent of tensile strength.

Microscopic observation of the free edge region indicated that the delamination occurred in the resin-rich region between θ and $-\theta$ layer as shown in Fig. 9. Since final fracture was imminent just after transverse cracking occurred in the delaminated region, the final load carrying capacity of these laminates could be assessed by using Eq. 4. The values of a^*/b semi-empirically determined from strength results with the above equation are in the range of .28 to .45. This prediction agrees reasonably with the value of .3 to .4 as shown in Fig. 5. However, the using of deply technique to determine the extent of delamination, a^*/b , was not successful because of interaction between delamination and transverse cracking. Fig. 10 shows delamination fracture surfaces observed in the SEM. Some fiber debonds are observed and the matrix resin on the crack surface is shown to have undergone extensive plastic deformation. It is hard to distinguish the effects of cohesive and adhesive failures on the overall fracture behavior of delamination. The surface energy for seperating adhesive fiber/matrix interfacial surfaces is expected to be of the same order of magnitudes as that for generating cohesive matrix crack surfaces[24]. The surface energy, cohesive or adhesive, involving polymers such as epoxy is much smaller than the total fracture energy dissipated by the delamination[21,22,24]. Therefore, the matrix plastic deformation named serration[25] observed on the fracture surfaces should be considered as a major energy dissipation mechanism in mode III delamination fracture process. Also, it was shown that the tilted serrations lie between fiber imprints and align more or less perpendicular to the fiber imprints. This phenomenon is caused by the relative rotation

Fig.9 Delamination crack in 15/-15 interfaces.

$\theta = 10^\circ$

$\theta = 15^\circ$

$\theta = 20^\circ$

$\theta = 30^\circ$

Fig.10 SEM photograph of delaminated fracture surface in $[\pm\theta]_s$ laminates

Table 2 Tensile Test Results

Fiber Orientation (degree)	$E_{xx}/E_{xx})_p$	σ_f^i/σ_f^u	$\sigma_f^u/\sigma_f^u)_p$
10	0.99	0.92	0.60
15	1.05	0.88	0.78
20	1.05	0.90	0.76
30	0.98	0.48	1.1

* subscript "p" means predicted value

E_{xx} : Axial stiffness

σ_f^i : Initial failure stress

σ_f^u : Ultimate tensile strength

due to the opposite sign of shear coupling constants between the adjacent plies at the delamination crack tip.

CONCLUSION

The onset and growth of free edge delamination of angle-ply laminate subjected to mechanical and thermal loading have been analyzed in this study by using strain energy release rate concept in linear elastic fracture mechanics. And experimental observations were made to assess the theoretical model. Based on the present results the following conclusions may be drawn.

The behavior of delamination is influenced by the fiber orientation, ply thickness, thermal residual stress and loading conditions. The presence of thermal residual stress plays a significant role on the initiation and propagation of delamination according to the loading condition. Mode III is dominant fracture mode of free edge delamination and stable growth region exists after unstable growth near the free edge. In the experimental phase, microscopic observations of fracture mechanisms revealed that delamination is clearly a matrix dominated failure occurring in the resin-rich interlaminar region. Present analysis which considers the effect of delamination predicts better results of strength than failure theory for small fiber orientations. Delamination should be taken into account of strength evaluation of angle-ply composites.

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